

Correlation between oil substrates and biosurfactant activity using *Acinetobacter junii* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

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Manuscript received online 14 September 2012, revised 10 June 2013, accepted 14 June 2013

Abstract : Two potential biosurfactant producing microorganisms – *Acinetobacter junii* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were isolated from oil contaminated soils and air. The aim of this work was to evaluate the comparative potential of these two microorganisms in utilizing different vegetable and mineral oils as substrate for production of biosurfactant. The effect of pH and temperature on biosurfactant production by these two microorganisms was also evaluated. High molecular weight, high boiling mineral oils e.g. diesel resulted in better surface activity with *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and produced rhamnolipid type of biosurfactant. The trend was reverse for *Acinetobacter junii* which produced proteoglycan type biosurfactant of comparatively less activity using petrol (low molecular weight and low boiling mineral oil fraction) as substrate. In case of vegetable oils, unsaturated C16 and C18 containing substrates were more effective for biosurfactant production especially for *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Optimum pH for *Acinetobacter junii* was 7.0 where as optimum growth of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was observed at pH 7.5. Optimum temperature for growth of both microorganisms was 30 °C. This study has thus screened and identified two microorganisms viz. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Acinetobacter junii* for biosurfactant production using different vegetable and mineral oils as substrate. The biosurfactant produced by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* had better surface activity considering both surface tension and emulsification index.

Keywords : Biosurfactant, *Acinetobacter junii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, surface tension, emulsification stability, vegetable oils, mineral oils.

Introduction

Biosurfactants are surface-active substances synthesized by microbial cells which adhere to cell-surfaces or are excreted extracellularly in the growth medium. As they contain both hydrophobic and hydrophilic moieties, they have the ability to partition between fluid layers thus reducing surface and interfacial tension. They can stabilize emulsions, promote foaming and are generally non-toxic and biodegradable. In recent years, interest in biosurfactants has been generated because of some specific properties such as low toxicity, good biodegradability and ecological acceptability¹ which confer them being more advantageous than chemically synthesized surfactants. They have versatile uses in the fields of enhanced oil recovery, environment bioremediation, food processing, pharmaceutical industry, paper and pulp industry and can be used for uranium ore-processing and mechanical dewatering of peat¹⁻³. Biosurfactants enhance

the emulsification of hydrocarbons and have the potential to solubilize hydrocarbon contaminants and increase their availability for microbial degradation. Thus, biosurfactant producing microorganisms play an important role in the accelerated bioremediation of hydrocarbon contaminated sites^{4,5}.

Several reports are available on the production of surface active compounds by microorganisms using water-immiscible substrates^{6,7}. Production of emulsifier by a strain of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (C1 LBPVMA-UFAL) using lubricating oil as main carbon source has been reported⁵. When grown on hydrocarbon substrates as the carbon source, these microorganisms synthesize a wide range of compounds such as glycolipid, phospholipid and others with surface activity^{8,9}. These compounds are apparently synthesized to emulsify the hydrocarbon substrate and facilitate its transport into the cells. Rhamnolipids from *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, surfactin from *Bacillus*

subtilis, emulsan from *Acinetobacter calcoaceticus* and sophorolipids from *Candida bombicola* are some examples of microbial-derived surfactants¹⁰. Most biosurfactants are either anionic or neutral and the hydrophobic moiety is based on long-chain fatty acids or fatty acid derivatives, whereas the hydrophilic portion can be a carbohydrate, amino acid, phosphate or cyclic peptide. Production of rhamnose containing glycolipid was first described by Jarvis and Johnson¹¹ with *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The rhamnolipids are the best studied class of biosurfactants produced by several species of the genus *Pseudomonas* which is capable of using different substrates, such as glycerol, mannitol, fructose, glucose, *n*-paraffins and vegetable oils, to produce rhamnolipid-type biosurfactants^{8,12}. *Acinetobacter* species are reported to produce high molecular weight biosurfactants and bioemulsans are the best studied ones. These biosurfactants are composed of polysaccharides, proteins, lipopolysaccharides, lipoproteins or complex mixtures of these polymers¹³. The two commonly used parameters to quantify biosurfactant production are surface tension measurement and emulsification index¹⁴. Surface tension and biosurfactant concentration are interrelated; the higher reduction of surface tension could be correlated with higher production of biosurfactant in the medium¹⁵. In earlier reports 12 isolates derived from a Long Beach soil, California (USA) and a Hong Kong soil (China), contaminated with diesel oil were tested for emulsification activity and surface tension lowering activity. It was observed that *Acinetobacter junii* displayed the highest reduction of surface tension (46.5 mN m^{-1}) compared to the other isolates such as *Bacillus cereus*, *Bacillus sphaericus*, *B. fusiformis*, *Pseudomonas sp.* and *B. pumilus*¹⁶.

The present investigation evaluates the potential of two strains of microorganism, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Acinetobacter junii* to produce biosurfactants when exposed to different kinds of mineral oils and vegetable oils. A systematic study was made using (a) mineral oils of different boiling ranges as well as pure hydrocarbons of varying carbon no./molecular weight and (b) a number of vegetable oils varying in saturated and unsaturated fatty acid content. A comparative evaluation of the biosurfactants produced using various substrates with respect to surface tension lowering activity and emulsification activity was conducted. Optimizations of physical

parameters for maximum production of biosurfactants were also studied for all the substrates used.

Results and discussion

Isolation and identification of micro-organisms :

Acinetobacter junii was isolated from oil contaminated soil and was identified by 16 S rDNA (GenBank accession no. AM410704). *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was isolated from air. Based on nucleotide homology and phylogenetic analysis, *Pseudomonas sp.* was identified (Accession No. DQ305287). The sequence aligned gave 100% similarity with *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Accession No. FJ227280).

Optimization of pH and temperature for maximum biosurfactant production :

Optimizing factors that affect growth of biosurfactant producing organisms is of paramount importance for their commercial exploitation⁹. Changes of pH affect substrate utilization and also directly influence bacterial growth which in turn causes changes in biosurfactant activity. The optimum pH for *Acinetobacter junii* was found to be 7. Similar results with *Acinetobacter* strains were reported when almond oil has been used as a substrate¹⁷. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* showed optimum growth when the pH was 7.5. This is also in consonance with reports of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* showing maximum biosurfactant production at pH 7.5 using 2% diesel as the substrate¹⁸ (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Effect of pH of the culture medium on surface tension activity of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Acinetobacter junii* (ST values expressed as mean \pm SE, $n = 3$).

Both the organisms showed optimum growth rate at 30 °C (Fig. 2). Change in temperature may cause alter-

Fig. 2. Effect of temperature on surface tension activity of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Acinetobacter junii* (ST values expressed as mean ±SE, *n* = 3).

ations in the composition of the biosurfactant as reported by others^{19,20}. Information regarding effect of temperature on rhamnolipid production with *P. aeruginosa* strains has been lacking thus, temperature is one of the critical parameters that have to be considered during biosurfactant production. Rhamnolipid production was also found to be maximum by indigenous *P. aeruginosa* in the temperature range 30 °C to 37 °C by other workers²¹.

Evaluation of biosurfactant activity :

(i) *Study of surface tension :*

Both *Acinetobacter junii* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* showed surface tension (ST) lowering activity with mineral oils as well as vegetable oils after 24 h of incubation and reached a maximum after 120 h.

As the boiling range of the mineral oil substrate increases in the order : Petrol < Kerosene < Diesel, the surface activity produced by *Acinetobacter junii* decreases but the observation was just reverse for the *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Table 1). This was supported by the study using pure hydrocarbons as substrate (Table 2). For *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* the surface activity increases as the boiling point of the substrate as well as molecular weight or carbon number increases in the order :

Table 1. Surface tension (ST) and emulsification index (E24) of different mineral oils

Types of mineral oils	<i>Acinetobacter junii</i>		<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	
	ST (mNm ⁻¹)	E24	ST (mNm ⁻¹)	E24
Petrol	44.5 ± 2.5	14.0	41.5 ± 2.39	20.0
Kerosene	51.0 ± 2.9	14.0	36.5 ± 2.10	23.0
Diesel	52.5 ± 3.03	12.0	34.5 ± 1.99	30.0

Results are expressed as mean ±SE, *n* = 3.

Table 2. Surface tension (ST) and emulsification index (E24) of different hydrocarbons

Types of hydrocarbons	<i>Acinetobacter junii</i>		<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	
	ST (mNm ⁻¹)	E24	ST (mNm ⁻¹)	E24
Hexadecane	42.5 ± 2.45	11.0	36.5 ± 2.10	57.0
Octadecane	46.0 ± 2.65	14.0	29.5 ± 1.70	59.0
Eicosane	52.0 ± 3.00	11.0	31.5 ± 1.82	45.0
Octacosane	51.0 ± 2.94	11.0	26.5 ± 1.53	10.7

Results are expressed as mean ±SE, *n* = 3.

Hexadecane < Octadecane < Eicosane < Octacosane and it attained the lowest surface tension value with Octacosane. However, for vegetable oils under study, the surface tension reduction ability of the biosurfactant was in the range of 28–31.0 mNm⁻¹ which is in the same range as reported earlier with *P. aeruginosa*²². In general, the surface activity was better with vegetable oils as compared to mineral oils which were observed particularly for *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Table 3). The surface tension lowering was maximum in case of sunflower oil for *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* where as it is minimum for Palm oil as supported by the observation when palmitic acid was used as the substrate (Table 4).

Table 3. Surface tension (ST) and emulsification index (E24) of different vegetable oils

Types of vegetable oils	<i>Acinetobacter junii</i>		<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	
	ST (mNm ⁻¹)	E24	ST (mNm ⁻¹)	E24
Sunflower oil	55.0 ± 3.17	14.0	28.5 ± 1.61	14.0
Ricebran oil	59.0 ± 3.40	10.5	29.5 ± 1.70	57.1
Groundnut oil	59.5 ± 3.4	12.0	31.5 ± 1.81	10.7
Soyabean oil	56.0 ± 3.23	13.0	30.5 ± 1.76	10.7
Palm oil	52.5 ± 3.03	11.0	32.5 ± 1.87	57.1
Olive oil	55.0 ± 3.17	10.0	31.0 ± 1.78	53.6

Results are expressed as mean ±SE, *n* = 3.

Table 4. Surface tension (ST) and emulsification index (E24) of different fatty acids

Types of fatty acids	<i>Acinetobacter junii</i>		<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	
	ST (mNm ⁻¹)	E24	ST (mNm ⁻¹)	E24
Palmitic acid	52.0 ± 3.00	14.0	39.5 ± 2.28	20.0
Stearic acid	52.5 ± 3.03	38.0	40.5 ± 2.34	22.0
Oleic acid	36.0 ± 2.07	11.0	32.0 ± 1.84	20.0

Results are expressed as mean ±SE, *n* = 3.

From the study with three types of fatty acids it was found that both the organisms produce biosurfactant of better activity from the unsaturated oleic acid as com-

pared to saturated palmitic and stearic acids. Composition of saturated and unsaturated fatty acids as well as the number of carbon atoms of the oils may lead to difference in biosurfactant activity of the vegetable oils or their feasibility to serve as a lipid precursor for rhamnolipid synthesis²².

(ii) *Study of emulsification stability (E24)* :

Emulsification activity is one of the criteria to select potential biosurfactant producers. Biosurfactant from *Acinetobacter junii* showed very little emulsification activity. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* showed higher emulsification activity with the hydrocarbon C16 and C18. Similar observation was found with vegetable oils like Rice bran oil, Palm oil containing C16 and C18 fatty acids (Tables 2 and 3). The E24 of the biosurfactant from *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was in the range of 20–60 which is supported by other workers²³.

Analysis of biosurfactant :

Carbohydrate, protein and lipid estimation of the biosurfactant produced by *Acinetobacter junii* was determined wherein protein and carbohydrate was found to be the major constituents (Table 5). It has been reported earlier that *Acinetobacter junii* produces proteoglycan type bioemulsifier¹⁷.

Table 5. Biochemical characterization of biosurfactants isolated from *Acinetobacter junii*

Chemical analysis	Carbohydrate (%)	Lipid (%)	Protein (%)
Purified extract ^a	63.14	32.31	4.5

^aPurified form of biosurfactant from *Acinetobacter junii* obtained by methods as described above.

In case of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, Molisch's test, rhamnose test and orcinol test were positive which indicated the presence of sugar moieties in the biosurfactant. The nature of biosurfactant was later confirmed to be of rhamnolipid type. Others also reported that *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolated from air produced rhamnolipid type biosurfactant when higher-paraffins i.e. C-12 onwards were used²⁴.

Thus both the bacterial strains, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Acinetobacter junii* are capable of producing biosurfactant effectively from various carbon sources and can degrade vegetable oils as well as mineral

oils. *Acinetobacter junii* produces proteoglycan type of biosurfactant whereas *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* produces rhamnolipid type of biosurfactant, but the latter has better surface activity considering both ST and E24 values.

Low boiling, low molecular weight mineral oils and hydrocarbon substrates are more effective for biosurfactant production with *Acinetobacter junii* but the reverse is true for *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. In case of vegetable oils, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is found to produce better biosurfactant with substrates containing C16 and C18 unsaturated fatty acids.

Experimental

Isolation and identification of Acinetobacter junii and Pseudomonas aeruginosa :

Soil samples contaminated with oil were collected from a number of petrol pumps situated at different locations in Kolkata. Bacteria were also isolated from contaminated air of the laboratory. Bacteria were isolated by the serial dilution technique using nutrient agar medium. Differential staining and biochemical tests were performed to identify the organisms which were confirmed by 16S rDNA sequencing techniques to be *Acinetobacter junii* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. These were sub-cultured using nutrient agar medium and maintained on nutrient agar slants for further experiments.

Medium and conditions for biosurfactant production :

Bacteria were inoculated on mineral salt agar medium¹⁵. Colonies grown on this media were inoculated (1 mL of inoculum contained 1×10^8 CFU) in mineral broth (50 mL) which contained 2% of oil (petrol, kerosene, diesel, vegetable oil) in sets of three flasks respectively. They were incubated for 5 days with shaking (175 rpm/min) or without shaking (in case of only *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*).

Biosurfactant recovery :

The culture broth was centrifuged (10000 g, 15 min) to remove the cells and thereafter sterilizing with membrane filter. The clear sterile supernatant served as the source of the crude biosurfactant. The biosurfactant was precipitated by acidifying supernatant to pH 2 with concentrated HCl and kept at 4 °C overnight. Next day after centrifugation at 12,000 g for 1 h, the precipitate was dissolved in deionized water. Two volumes of a mixture

of chloroform : methanol (2 : 1) was added for extraction of the biosurfactant. The organic phase was separated and evaporated to dryness in a rotary vacuum evaporator.

Chemical analysis of the biosurfactants/biochemical composition of the biosurfactant :

Chemical composition of the biosurfactants was analyzed following standard methods. The biosurfactant isolated from *Acinetobacter junii* was analyzed for its protein content using the method described by Lowry *et al.*²⁶. Lipid was estimated by adopting the procedure of Folsch *et al.*²⁷. The content of carbohydrate in the biosurfactant was determined by reacting with phenol-sulphuric acids reagent and the absorbances of samples were measured at 485 nm against dilute sulphuric acid²⁸.

Molisch's test was done to detect the presence of sugar in the biosurfactant produced by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Rhamnose was found by the method of Dubois *et al.*²⁹ and confirmed by the Orcinol assay³⁰. The rhamnolipid concentration was evaluated based on a standard curve prepared with different concentrations of L-rhamnose (equivalent to mg rhamnose mL⁻¹). All results were estimated in triplicates.

Effect of pH and temperature on biosurfactant production :

The effect of pH and temperature on the production of biosurfactant by the bacteria was studied with changing ambient conditions and optimized.

The pH of the medium was adjusted with phosphate buffer and varied from 6.0 to 8.5 and the temperature was varied in the range 25–42 °C.

Screening for biosurfactant activity :

Biosurfactant activity of isolated bacteria was detected using measurement of surface tension and emulsification index (E24) with different types of mineral and vegetable oils namely petrol, kerosene, diesel, sunflower, rice-bran, ground-nut, soyabean, palm and olive oil. A number of fatty acids and hydrocarbons were also studied to compare the activity of the biosurfactants produced by *Acinetobacter junii* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

Determination of surface tension :

Surface tension was determined using a Du-Nouy ring tensiometer (K11, Krüss, Hamburg, Germany) by standard methods. All measurements were made on cell-free

broth obtained after centrifuging the culture media at 10000 rpm for 15 min at room temperature (25 ± 2 °C).

Determination of emulsification index (E24) :

E24 of culture samples was determined by adding 2 ml of oil to the same amount of culture filtrate, mixing with a vortex for 2 min and leaving it to stand for 24 h at 25 °C. The height of the emulsion layer was measured thereafter to determine the emulsification index. The E24 index is given as percentage of height of emulsified layer (mm) divided by total height of the liquid column (mm)³¹. The equation used to determine the emulsification index (E24) is as follows :

$$E24 = \frac{\text{Height of total solution}}{\text{Height of emulsion layer}} \times 100\%$$

Acknowledgement

We wish to thank Ms. Rakhi Banik Chowdhury, Research Scholar, and Mr. Plabon Bhattacharya, CSIR-SRF, Department of Chemical Technology, University of Calcutta, for their untiring support in analyzing the biosurfactant. Research associateship to Ms. Runa Ghosh Auddy from CRNN, University of Calcutta is gratefully acknowledged.

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